

The Effectiveness Of A Training Program To Develop The Level Of Educational Competencies For Teachers Of Kindergarten Children With Integrated Autism Spectrum Disorder In Jordan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 13, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: June 25, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Training Program, Educational Competencies, Teachers, Kindergarten, Autism Spectrum Disorder</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5033276</p>	<p><i>The current study aimed to uncover the effectiveness of a training program to develop the level of educational competencies for teachers of preschool students with integrated autism spectrum disorder in Jordan. The sample of the study consisted of (40) female teachers who were randomly selected from the teachers of kindergarten students with autism spectrum disorder. They were divided into two groups: the control group, and it consisted of (20) teachers and the experimental group (20) teachers. And the educational competencies scale of female teachers of students with autism spectrum disorder was used, which consisted of (5) fields and (63) paragraphs. And the application of the training program. The results of the study showed that there were statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the mean of the study sample according to the group variables (control, experimental) in the level and fields of educational competencies, and in favor of the experimental group. The study concluded with several recommendations, most notably the amendment of policies and practices related to inclusive programs in public schools in kindergartens with autism spectrum disorder.</i></p>

Introduction

Introduction and theoretical framework:

The kindergarten stage aims at the comprehensive and balanced development of students with autism spectrum disorder, whether physical, mental, emotional, or social, through the process of learning and education, and to exploit their senses and perceptions as outlets for knowledge, and to provide a psychologically safe and culturally exciting environment for them. The teachers of kindergarten students with autism spectrum disorder integrated in public schools play a major and important role in building the personality of the student with the various knowledge, values, attitudes and competencies she possesses, which she invests in developing his abilities and capabilities, and satisfying his various needs properly, as they are responsible for everything that the student learns and what is related to. In order to achieve the requirements of his growth at this critical stage, teachers of kindergarten students with autism spectrum disorder and workers in educational institutions must be prepared, qualified and trained in order to bring about the desired change in the level of staff performance and provide them with the information, experiences, methods of dealing and working with the most advanced with this group, as well as patterns of behavior and trends. Positivity that helps them conduct their business with high efficiency.

The Ministry of Education in Jordan is keen on the continuity of work according to the strategic planning approach to achieve sectoral and national goals. To meet the challenges of the twenty-first century, keep abreast of various developments, and improve the quality of education and educational services provided to learners in all regions of the Kingdom. The Ministry has prepared the strategic plan for the years 2018-2022 with a participatory approach, with the broad contribution of all departments and directorates of education, and in continuous coordination and follow-up with the International Institute for Educational Planning in France and UNESCO (Ministry of Education, 2018-2022).

Within the framework of the Ministry's endeavor to achieve the goals of the National Strategy for Human Resources Development 2016-2025, Jordan Vision 2025, and the Sustainable Development Goals, the Ministry focused its plan objectives around long-term strategic options based on an integrated analysis of the internal and external environment, and identifying the elements of strength and opportunities for improvement related to the areas governing the process. Education, and the strategic directions of the education sector in Jordan, highlighting the opportunities and challenges facing the Ministry, with analytical participation with partners and

stakeholders. The Ministry of Education has established a monitoring and evaluation mechanism, with the aim of periodically evaluating the course of planning and implementation, within procedures that contribute to strengthening institutional and accountability in the educational process. To improve the quality of education, raise the quality of its outputs, and establish competitiveness in this vital sector. (Ministry of Education, 2018-2022).

The Ministry has paid more attention to the kindergarten stage. By increasing enrollment in pre-school education, which highlighted the importance of enhancing institutional efficiency, raising the skills of teachers and workers, as well as strengthening community partnership. To ensure access and equality for all students; To realize the vision of education for all and justice for both sexes with disabilities; In light of the issuance of the Rights of Persons with Disabilities Law No. 20 of 2017 by accommodating all age groups, providing a stimulating educational environment, educational, awareness and health programs, developing infrastructure for students with disabilities, and providing qualified and trained educational personnel to deal with students with disabilities. (Ministry of Education, 2018-2022).

Providing qualified human resources and building sustainable development programs to enhance the capabilities of teachers and enable them to achieve educational outcomes efficiently and effectively requires a career path for teachers that integrates in its context all aspects related to teachers in a common frame of reference, including a system of ranks and incentives, and stimulates the motivation of teachers in the professional stages. Main and expected development. By pursuing an integrated policy, to track the quality of teaching and learning, and to keep pace with the rapid development of information and communication technology. Under this policy, smart electronic learning resources and their maintenance, and the development of the quality of electronic services provided by the ministry. (Ministry of Education Vision, 2025).

Early intervention and ongoing support in kindergarten for students with autism spectrum disorder and in various contexts is of critical importance to ensuring the right to a comprehensive and appropriate curriculum that provides access to the necessary knowledge, skills, and social and cultural values available to all individuals within the community (Guldberg, 2010).

Interest in early intervention in the kindergarten stage also increased after the signing of the Convention on Human Rights and the Rights of the Child, which stipulates the right of children to obtain the health services they need and aspects of psychological, social, life and academic care regardless of their age, as early intervention services contribute to preventing or reducing as much as possible of the risk factors that impede the child's development, whether they are physical, healthy, cognitive, and cognitive. (U.S. Department of Education, 2013; IDEA, 2011).

In-service training is extremely important to educational institutions, as these institutions are concerned with preparing and educating teachers as the most important element of development. Training must include all kindergarten teachers in the educational institution at all administrative levels in order to bring about change in the level of individual performance in terms of providing them with more information, experiences and methods of work. Development and modernization, as well as the positive behavior patterns and trends that help them to practice their work efficiently (Haidar, 2005).

Therefore, educational training carried out by most ministries and educational institutions in the world is an important matter in the number of their human cadres during service, as the theoretical educational thought translates into practical application in the field of work, and paves the way for human competencies in the expression of advanced educational thought that would improve the level of The performance of educational institutions and raises the quality of their educational outputs at the level of achievement, character building, and preparing them for the educational and life future (Al-Kurdi, 2008).

Autism spectrum disorder is a lifelong condition that affects the way a person communicates and their relationship with other people and the world around them (Daly et al., 2016). It is a spectrum case; It means that all people with autism share some traits, but it affects them in different and heterogeneous ways (Jonens & Jordan, 2008). Students with autism spectrum disorder can learn and develop in different ways than regular students (Jordan, 2005).

There are four main areas of difference that affect how a student with autism spectrum disorder learns in early education or early school years (Guldbrg at al., 2011), namely: (1) the existence of different ways of understanding communication and language (gestures, facial expressions, voice) . (2) This interdependence will be closely related in understanding social behavior, feelings and emotions. (3) The processing of interests and information affects how the student understands the world around him and the information processing, planning,

generalization and prediction, in addition to shifts, feelings, or interests. (4) Differences in perception of sensory information can lead to low or high sensitivity in any of the senses (Guldborg et al., 2016).

As a result of the heterogeneous nature of autism spectrum disorder. Taking into account individual capabilities and needs, they need support in a range of areas. It includes developing the skills, knowledge and understanding necessary to acquire the ability to: (1) Communicate effectively in social situations. (2) Forming and maintaining relationships. (3) Predicting and managing change. (4) Understanding the curriculum. (5) Achieving educational objectives in the educational program. (6) Adapting and managing the classroom environment to reduce the impact of sensory processing problems. (7) Regulating behaviors, emotions and excitement. (8) Interacting With repetitive behavioral patterns. (9) Generalize the behaviors and skills acquired in similar environments, whether at home or in society (Bond et al., 2015).

Evidence from research studies highlighted the need for a framework for professional and personal development, from awareness-raising to a broader level of accreditation and licensure. Standards and quality indicators should also be considered to help staff working with autism spectrum disorder to acquire skills and knowledge at a high level of quality. An example is the United Kingdom, see (www.autismeducationtrust.co.uk), where there are high levels of skills, knowledge and training among the cadres in increasing cooperation with the multidisciplinary team in an integrative and coordinated manner to work for the development of online information resources that increase the level of awareness about these Category and the development of national training programs for working cadres, including teachers, administrators, and students' families, and providing them at the university level. Participants also participated in the Autism Education Trust program. In setting up a special professional development program in England. This partnership brought together major sectors of society to cooperate in developing three areas for involving cadres working in the field of education with their knowledge and practices with the autism spectrum disorder group linked to national standards, from professional development, to comprehensive school development by setting common goals for acceptable practices for people with autism spectrum disorder and facilitating the evaluation process Self in schools. In it, the framework defines the competency, practices and key knowledge needed by the cadres working in these schools who have autism spectrum disorder. In these areas. This provides educational and administrative staff with a framework for assessing and monitoring their skills and determining their needs in training and professional development programs. In Australia, the Center for Collaborative Research on Autism Spectrum Disorder is supporting collaboration led by the private sector, society and researchers to develop vocational training and manage a range of projects. (www.autismeducationtrust.co.uk).

In view of the educational institutions' lack of targeted goals facing their course, which depend most of the time on goals that are comprehensive, general and unclear, it may cast doubt on the ability of these institutions to achieve their goals or the ability to evaluate as the Faculties of Education in universities and teachers' institutes undertake the pre-service teacher preparation. While the Ministry of Education undertakes its preparation during the service, and due to the lack of cooperation and coordination between the Faculties of Education and the Ministry of Education and Education, we notice a discrepancy between preparing the teacher before service and qualifying during the service. (Hanafi, 2007).

As Rosenberg & Walther (2014) sees, the needs of special education teachers are continuous in more than one field, and therefore there is a need to continue the process of preparing them during the service, to train them on how to deal with the curriculum for children with special needs, assessment procedures and other competencies.

Determining training needs is the first pillar in planning training programs, and many of those interested in education have emphasized that identifying the needs of the trainees is the first step in building and designing any successful training program that achieves its objectives. (Zwelff, 2008) summarized this importance in the following points:

(1) The process of determining the needs is the real factor behind raising the efficiency of the workers in performing the tasks assigned to them.

(2) It is considered the basis upon which any training program is based. (3) It works to direct the capabilities available for training to the right direction. (4) Its importance also lies in the detection of Training needs in advance, which leads to saving effort, money and time spent in training, and reveals any problems and obstacles that the teacher may face.

It is clear from the above that there is a set of professional competencies required for special education teachers in the kindergarten stage. Among the most important of these competencies: the ability to detect and collect information from its sources, the ability to apply diagnostic tests (developmental and academic), the ability to analyze patterns of errors and study them to find out the strategy used by the student during the answer, the ability to write a diagnostic report identifying the student's problem in a scientific manner, and to make decisions. Recommendations, determining the current performance level, identifying strengths and

shortcomings due to their importance in designing the individual educational plan and the educational educational plan, the skill of formulating behavioral goals (long-term and short-term), taking into account individual differences when formulating goals and methods of evaluating them, preparing daily for educational activities, and choosing appropriate teaching strategies. For the student and diversifying it, using the appropriate educational means for the educational goal, mastering the scientific material and the ability to achieve its goals, choosing appropriate reinforcement methods for the student, managing the classroom and arranging the classroom environment in the form of educational stations, and the students' participation in dialogue and discussion, taking their opinions, taking into account their preferences and attitudes, and the participation of the family. In the individual educational program for the student, write the goals that pertain to them (plan Family services). Emphasizing the importance of continuous cooperation and communication between teachers, the multidisciplinary team, the school administration, and the families of students with autism spectrum disorder.

The study problem and its questions

Some international and local organizations and some countries interested in the kindergarten stage in the twenty-first century have sought to develop specifications and standards for the profession of kindergarten teachers, such as the National Association for the Education of Young Children (NAEYC, 2009), and the Center for Studies of Early Childhood Cadres (Bellm, 2008), all of which confirm The need to start children's education in early childhood. The Jordanian Ministry of Education and Education sought to achieve the goals of the National Strategy for Human Resources Development 2016-2025, and the Ministry focused its plan to establish a monitoring and evaluation mechanism, with the aim of periodically evaluating the course of planning and implementation, within procedures that contribute to strengthening institutional and accountability in the educational process. To improve the quality of education, raise the quality of its outputs, and establish competitiveness in this vital sector. Some reports related to kindergarten education emphasized that the existing programs and curricula do not reflect the correct method of human education, nor do they help thinking according to the higher levels that have become the requirements of the current century (Ramo, 2013). In addition, programs for preparing female teachers in kindergarten in the Arab world, including Jordan, still suffer from many challenges, shortcomings and weaknesses, especially for special education teachers for those with autism spectrum disorder. We find that previous studies conducted in the field of educational competence for teachers of students with special needs, including the study (Al-Batayneh, 2014) indicated the need to evaluate the educational competencies of teachers of children with special needs in Jordan in order to improve them, and the study (Al-Khatib and Al-Hadidi, 2010), which indicated that Special education teachers in Jordan, especially beginners, face great professional challenges when moving from the university to the field of work, because they find many differences between what they are prepared for at the university and what they find in the field, which affects their professional personality, self-confidence, and study (Yahya (2007), which indicated the need to use vocational training programs for special education teachers in Jordan, and the study (Gharib, (2007), which indicated the importance of an approach with competencies in the formation of teachers for children with special needs in Morocco, and the study (Al-Dhaen, 2005), which indicated the necessity of training Working with people with disabilities and proposals for their development in the Kingdom of Bahrain, (Masoud, 2004) which showed that field training has a clear effect on improving the personal and professional growth and educational competencies of students of the Department of Education of Saudi Arabia.

Based on the theoretical framework and previous studies presented, the study problem becomes clear in the apparent deficiency in the level of professional skills and competencies of kindergarten teachers with autism spectrum disorder in Jordan, and the scarcity of research on training programs for female teachers, and the researchers see the importance of improving and improving professional and personal competencies And among the teachers of kindergarten students with autism spectrum disorder, within specific and clear criteria, by preparing a training program for this goal, which will form the beginning of the way in planning and preparing for such training programs during the service.

Therefore, the problem of the current study was determined by answering the following question?

1-How effective is a training program for teachers of kindergarten students with autism spectrum disorder in developing the level of competencies of kindergarten teachers in the governorate of Irbid ?

2-Are there statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) in developing the level of educational competencies of the teachers of the kindergarten students with autism spectrum disorder integrated in Irbid governorate between the control group and the experimental group ?

Objectives of the study:

1-Preparing a training program to develop the level of educational competencies for teachers of pre-school students with autism spectrum disorder integrated in the governorate of Irbid in Jordan.

2-Disclosure of the effectiveness of the proposed training program, and its role in developing the level of educational competencies of the teachers of students with integrated autism spectrum disorder in the governorate of Irbid in Jordan.

The importance of studying:

The importance of the current study was determined in the following points:

The theoretical importance: it is hoped that this study will help raise the attention of officials in charge of drawing up public policies related to the field of training and vocational training programs for kindergarten teachers for those with autism spectrum disorders in Jordan, and in developing and implementing such programs with high efficiency and effectiveness.

Application importance: Shedding light on the reality of in-service vocational training programs in preparing kindergarten teachers with autism spectrum disorder. The apparent deficiency in the level of skills and competencies of female kindergarten teachers with autism spectrum disorder, and the scarcity of research on training programs for female teachers in Jordan.

Providing a note card for students regarding the competencies of female teachers with autism spectrum disorder in the field of teaching planning, the educational program and services provided, diagnosis and evaluation, and the educational environment.

Theoretical and procedural definitions:

The educational competencies of female teachers: a set of knowledge, skills, procedures and trends that a teacher needs to do her work with the least cost, effort and time, and without which she cannot perform her duty, and then her availability should be considered a condition for her permission to work. (Al-Khatib, and others, (2008)

Educational competencies of female teachers, procedurally: a set of measurable cognitive, mental, psychological, social and physical skills and abilities that enable the teacher to perform activities in kindergarten with a good level of effectiveness, to achieve the educational goals related to kindergarten students with autism spectrum disorder. Which can be observed and evaluated through the scale of learning competencies.

The training program: It is an ongoing organized process that aims to bring about specific behavioral, artistic and mental changes to meet current or future needs required by the individual and the work he performs and the institution in which he works (Hamat, 2007).

It is defined procedurally: as the training program and its content that was prepared by the researcher, and aims to develop the competencies of kindergarten teachers for people with autism spectrum disorder.

People with autism spectrum disorders: They are those who show clear deficits in communication skills, social interaction, stereotypical, repetitive and ritual behaviors (APA, 2013.p49).

Autism spectrum disorders are procedurally defined: they are students with autism who are enrolled in kindergarten schools who are integrated into the school in Jordan, and have been diagnosed by the official specialized centers.

The limits of the study:

Time limits: The current study was limited to the year (2020/2021).

Spatial boundaries: This study was limited to the governorate of Irbid in Jordan.

Human limits: The study sample was restricted to teachers of kindergarten students with autism spectrum disorder in Irbid Governorate, Jordan.

Objective limits: Preparing a training program to develop educational competencies for teachers of kindergarten students with autism spectrum disorder in Irbid Governorate, Jordan.

Previous studies:

The study of Al-Jadoua and Al-Momani (2020) aimed to investigate the effectiveness of a training program based on individual play activities in improving the skills of imitation and response, and used the pre-experimental approach. Of those with autism spectrum disorder after their psychometric characteristics were reached, and the results of the study indicated that there was a statistically significant effect in the level ($\alpha = 05.0$) between the pre and post measurement in improving imitation skill due to the training program, and the results also indicated the presence of a significant effect Statistical significance at ($\alpha = 05.0$) level between pre and post measurement in improving response skill attributed to the training program. In light of the results of the study, the researchers recommended that attention should be paid to including imitation and response skills as a basic requirement in educational and therapeutic programs for autistic children.

Autism teacher that is competence is able to educate autism child that are increasing throughout the year. The aim of this study is to identify the competency of special education teacher in teaching autistic child and curriculum in teacher training. This study used quantitative approaches and questionnaire is built to collect the data. A total of 107 primary teachers in Jasin Melaka have been selected by purposive sampling for this survey. The study found that special education teachers are less competency in using evidence based teaching for autism. Data shows that most of the teachers have not received any training in how to teach autistic child during teaching training in university or teacher training center. This study is important to modify the current teacher training course related to autism to increase the quality of teachers.

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Al-Tabal conducted a study (2019) aimed at identifying the reality of inclusive education programs in kindergartens in Jordan, and the study sample consisted of (165) governmental and private kindergartens distributed over the three regions. In order to achieve the objectives of the study, an inclusive education evaluation tool in kindergartens was prepared, which was divided into two main axes (88) indicators. The physical educational environment axis consists of (44) indicators, and the social environment axis, which consists of (44) indicators. The study reflected the reality of inclusive education in kindergarten schools in Jordan, which was implemented by the Supreme Council for the Rights of Persons with Disabilities.

Among the most important results indicated by the study is that no governorate enjoys adequate provision of inclusive education requirements, especially government ones, and indicated the small number of kindergartens that implement inclusive education in the southern governorates. The results reflected the lack of specific educational programs used in kindergartens, which affected the effectiveness of inclusive education in some kindergartens and the formation of negative attitudes towards it by some departments, teachers and some parents of students enrolled in them.

In a qualitative study conducted by each of (Kwon, Hong & Amorimc, 2018), it examined the correlation between the experiences of teachers in working with children with disabilities (such as education, specialized training and years of scientific experience), their attitudes towards children with disabilities and their academic practices regarding inclusive education. In early childhood stage, in addition to studying the correlation between children's attitudes towards their peers with disabilities and variables related to children and teachers, ninety-one children within the age group (4-5 years) and their teachers were interviewed. The results of the study indicated that there is a positive correlation between training distinguished teachers and obtaining a bachelor's degree in early childhood education (ESE) on the one hand, and positive inclusive education practices in the classroom. The previous experiences of children in dealing with persons with disabilities were positively linked to their attitudes towards children with disabilities and inclusive education, and to the need to provide opportunities for social interaction and communication with children with disabilities in order to modify attitudes towards them and facilitate their receiving of quality education in inclusive education environments.

The study of Al-Ba'irat (2018) aimed to know the readiness of regular public schools in Jordan, with the available preparations, equipment and elements For the success of integrating students with disabilities, as the study sample consisted of (112) schools in which integration programs are applied north, middle and south, and to achieve the goal of the study, the researcher prepared a tool for measuring readiness in regular government schools affiliated with the Ministry of Education, and the tool consisted of 4 Areas of which are: (1) Workers, who are administrators, the regular teacher, and the special education teacher. (2) Parents. ((3) Ordinary students. (4) And the physical environment. The validity and reliability of the study tool was verified, and the descriptive and analytical approach was followed, and the results of the study indicated that government regular schools were not prepared to integrate students with disabilities in Jordan, as the readiness associated with management and workers came first. While the readiness associated with the special education teacher came in the last rank. It also indicated the difference in the readiness of regular government schools according to the difference in the impact of the school's sex, and it came in favor of female schools. (20) students or less, while the results of the study showed that the readiness of government regular schools did not differ according to the effect of the type of disability suffered by students with disabilities.

Barton & Smith (2015) conducted a survey that aimed to determine whether team members believed that children with disabilities show improvement in their skills through inclusive early childhood education. As one hundred percent of the participants in this study indicated that there is a significant development in the social skills of children who enroll in inclusive education in kindergarten and the formation of friendships between children with disabilities and their looks in preschool classrooms. Most of the participants confirmed that children with disabilities showed improvement in their language skills in comprehensive inclusion settings, and more than half of the participants confirmed that academic skills improve in inclusive learning environments, and that (87%) parents of other children without disabilities also support it.

The results of a survey conducted by each (Barton & Smith, 2015) on the Internet and aimed at identifying the challenges of inclusive education in the pre-school stage, with the participation of hundreds of education managers and teachers in the kindergarten and special education stage, indicated that the attitudes and beliefs of workers are one in terms of the main challenges To develop and implement inclusive education programs in pre-school. The lack of communication and cooperation between kindergarten teachers and special education teachers, the training of kindergarten staff to provide high-quality services, and the lack of understanding of the facts about inclusive education in the pre-school stage were among the most important sources of concern. Moreover, policies and procedures were in the second degree a challenge to the success of inclusive education. These general policies relate to pre-school care and education, policies related to the quality of training programs, incentives for workers, and ease of transportation to work sites, in addition to curricula. The final challenge identified in this survey is related to financial and professional resources. The respondents identified the lack of places for children in community programs, the lack of transportation, in addition to the difficulty of accessing sign language interpreting services, speech and language correction services (pronunciation), occupational therapy and physical therapy.

In a survey study (Electa, 2014) published by the Department of Early Learning and Technical Assistance Challenge at the University of Colorado to highlight the obstacles that prevent the inclusion of children with disabilities in pre-school, the study included hundreds of school principals and workers in the field of special education in childhood Early. The results of the study indicated that (30%) of the participants reported that negative attitudes and misconceptions about inclusive education were among the most important obstacles that prevented inclusive education in pre-school. In addition, (20%) indicated that the lack of communication or cooperation between programs and workers is one of the obstacles to integration. The results also indicated that (20%) indicated that some children will delay their abilities in inclusive education settings, while (17%) indicated that the poor numbers of teachers in inclusive education is one of the most important reasons that prevent successful integration, whether they are early childhood teachers. Or special education in early childhood and related services. Moreover, (16%) of them indicated that the lack of awareness of the reality of inclusive education at the pre-school level is one of the obstacles to high-quality inclusive education, and (14%) of them indicated that the weak relationship between workers in early childhood and special education is the reason. While (12%) of them indicated that the lack of appreciation of the programs and workers is the reason. Respondents identified policies and procedures as the second biggest challenge facing successful inclusion. They believed that it affects early childhood programs significantly, and more than a quarter of the responses indicated that public policies related to early care and education pose serious challenges to inclusive education, and the biggest challenges were effective financial policies such as contracting and funding programs, and inclusive education in non-governmental schools. Providing transportation for children to facilitate their access to an inclusive learning environment.

Each of (Lee, sandbank, & zymrman, 2014) conducted a study aimed at "identifying the training needs of special education teachers in Hong Kong", using the survey methodology, and the study sample included (275) teachers, regarding two factors: The first is the training needs of education teachers The second factor is the effectiveness of the training programs offered by the training centers, and the results indicated the need to take into account the opinions of teachers in the programs provided to them, and the study focused on preparing female teachers well during service through continuous training and providing them with more resources, and providing government support for what It has a great impact on building the effectiveness of female teachers in the workplace.

Al-Ghamdi (2013) conducted a study aimed at assessing the level of teaching skills of teachers of students with autism spectrum disorder, and then building a proposed training program to develop teaching skills and measure its effectiveness. The researcher prepared a list to monitor the teaching skills of teachers of students with Autism Spectrum Disorder, which consisted of (60) Paragraphs The study sample consisted of teachers of autism classes attached to regular schools in the western region of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, and the results of the post-measurement indicated the existence of statistically significant differences in favor of the experimental group, and showed that the improvement in teaching skills included all existing dimensions.

The study of (Ramo, 2013) aimed to measure the effectiveness of a competency-based training program in mastering the performance of kindergarten teachers in the city of Homs for their educational roles, which was applied to 20 kindergarten teachers. A training program was applied for female teachers. And the list of competencies of kindergarten teachers and a questionnaire surveying the opinions of teachers and mentors about the importance of the list of competencies and the training needs for it. The study found the effectiveness of the program through the presence of statistically significant differences in the positive trend between the pre and post applications of female teachers' attitudes towards each of: elements of the training program, training methods, evaluation tools, the use of modern teaching methods, and the trend towards continuous self-education. The study also showed that there are statistically significant differences in the academic achievement of the program content in favor of the post-test.

Hendricks (2011) conducted a study entitled "Training Needs Assessment for Special Education Teachers who Study Autistic Students" aimed at assessing the training needs of Special Education teachers who study students with Autism Spectrum Disorder in Virginia using an internet based survey, in which he responded to participate in This survey is about (498) teachers who are special education teachers. The study concluded the urgent need to prepare special education teachers in line with the nature of the disability they study, and teachers' possession of the knowledge and skills required to promote change, and provide basic data containing development implications for the development of personal requirements and training initiatives. And the use of modern technology methods and effective strategies to improve training.

The study (Al-Khatib, 2011) aimed to develop a proposed model for developing educational programs and services provided to children with mental disabilities and children with autism in special education institutions and centers in Jordan, in light of international standards.

The sample of the study consisted of all the study population from the institutions and centers of special education in the three regions of the Kingdom (center, north, and south) that provide educational programs and services for children with mental disabilities and children with autism and their number is (153) institutions and centers.

In order to collect data on the level of effectiveness of educational programs and services in institutions and centers of special education in Jordan, which provide their programs and services to children with mental disabilities and children with autism, two tools were built: A tool for evaluating the level of effectiveness of programs provided to children with mental disabilities. The tool consisted of eight dimensions and (89) key indicators. A tool to assess the level of effectiveness of programs provided to children with autism spectrum disorder. The tool consisted of eight dimensions (110) main indicators. Indications of the validity and reliability of the two tools were reached, which justified their use.

The results with regard to autism spectrum disorder indicated that there was one dimension that had a high level of effectiveness: the dimension of "services and programs" with an average of (0.68). Whereas, there were three dimensions with an average level of effectiveness, which are respectively: the "evaluation" dimension with an average (0.66), the "educational environment" dimension with an average (0.55), and the "management and workers" dimension with an average (0.37). As for the rest of the four dimensions, they were of a low level of effectiveness, namely: the "vision, thought and mission" dimension with an average of (0.33), "family participation, support and empowerment", the "integration and transitional services" dimension with an average of (0.31) for each, and the "evaluation dimension". Self "average (0.30).

Each of (Probst, & Leppert, 2008) presented a study aimed at measuring the impact of the training program for teachers of children with autism spectrum disorder on the basis of planning and organizing the teaching. A sample consisted of (10) teachers working with (10) students with autism spectrum disorder. The results resulted in a significant improvement in the behavioral symptoms of students in the classroom on the dimensional measurement, and a significant decrease in teachers' reactions about stress, and teachers used structured learning strategies every day by (9) out of (10) teachers by applying at least one strategy. It was applied mostly in the classroom, and the study results provided preliminary evidence of the social viability of the teaching program.

Commenting on previous studies:

Through the presentation of previous studies related to the subject of the current study, it is noticed the scarcity of studies that have investigated the development of the educational competencies of teachers of kindergarten students with autism spectrum disorders integrated in public schools. It is the goal of the current study, and we can see the importance and effectiveness of training programs for teachers of kindergarten students with autism spectrum disorder through developing their competencies, and it is noted from previous studies that they dealt with identifying the level of pre-service and in-service teacher training and the most important competencies required for teachers such as the Batayneh study (2014, And the study (Al-Khatib and Al-Hadidi, 2010), and the study (Lee, sandbank, & zymrman, 2014), which emphasized the preparation of teachers during service through

continuous training, and continuous support through government support, and the study (Al-Drummer, 2019), which confirmed its few The qualitative educational programs used in kindergarten for students with disabilities, as for the study (Barton & Smith, 2015), the results of which showed that the attitudes and beliefs of teachers and workers are one of the main challenges for developing and implementing education and training programs in the integrated kindergarten stage. 2011, its results confirmed the urgent necessity to prepare special education teachers in line with the nature of the disability they study, and that teachers possess the knowledge and skills required to promote change.

Based on the above, the study can be justified in terms of distinguishing it from previous studies within the limits of the researcher that it is one of the very few studies in Jordan that aims to uncover a training program in developing the competencies of kindergarten teachers with autism spectrum disorder, commensurate with the current study community and its Jordanian environment, and to provide data Fundamental that includes development contents for the development of personal requirements and training initiatives, and the use of modern technology methods and effective strategies to improve training programs.

Method and procedures:

Study Approach:

In this study, the researcher followed the quasi-experimental approach, "Quasi Experimental". This approach is based on the causal relationship between two variables, one of which is the independent or experimental variable and the other the dependent variable, given its suitability to treat the study variables.

Study population and sample:

The study population includes all teachers of students with autism spectrum disorder in kindergarten schools in the Kasbah of Irbid Governorate, which are 102 schools affiliated with the Jordanian Ministry of Education. And the number of female teachers working in kindergarten schools is (139) female. It serves students with autism spectrum disorder from the age of (4-5) years. The study sample consisted of (40) female teachers from students with autism spectrum disorder, who were chosen in a simple random way from the study population, and they were distributed into two groups, the first is the control group and consisted of (20) teachers, and the second was the experimental group and it consisted of (20) teachers. For the academic year 2020-2021, and the following table No. (1) illustrates this.

Table No. (1)

Distribution of the study sample

Variable	Number	Gender
Experimental Group	20	Females
Control Group	20	Females
Total	40	-

Study tools

First: Teaching Competencies Scale

For the purposes of determining and measuring the level of educational competencies of teachers of students with autism spectrum disorder integrated in kindergarten schools in Jordan, and to study the effectiveness of the developed training program, the scale was prepared in its preliminary form in light of a group of competencies reached according to the following procedures:

-Review theoretical literature, previous studies, research, and electronic databases. Among the most important studies and sources that were referred to in the construction of the scale (Al-Tabal, 2019; Electa,; 2018, Kwon, Hong & Amorimc, 2014; Barton & Smith, 2015; USDepartment of Education, 2013;; DMO, 2013; Al-Ghamdi, 2013; Al-Khatib, 2011; Al-Khatib, 2010; Probst, & Leppert, 2008; www.autismeducationtrust.co.uk; www.autismcrc.au).

-Determining the educational needs of female teachers, by reviewing the educational literature and previous studies related to developing the educational competency scale for female teachers of students with autism spectrum disorder.

-Limiting the fields of the educational competency scale for female teachers of students with autism spectrum disorder into (5) main areas

-Putting paragraphs on the five areas and arriving at the scale in its semi-final form. After these procedures, the scale consists of (63) items distributed on the five domains of the scale of educational competencies for students with autism spectrum disorder in kindergarten schools in Jordan, and Table No. (2) illustrates this.

Table No. (2)

The main areas of the educational competency scale for female teachers of students with autism spectrum disorder.

No.	The field	Items No.
1-	The First field: Planning for teaching	(8) items
2-	The second field: The educational curriculum consists of:	(26) items

	The individual educational program consists of (11) items.- Teaching methods and methods consist of (7) items.- -Behavior modification consists of (8) items.	
3-	The third field: Diagnosis and evaluation.	(9) items
4-	The fourth field: The teaching environment.	(11) items
5-	The fifth field: Inclusion and transitional services.	(9) items
The total		(63) items

The responses on this scale consisted of three levels according to the triple gradient according to Liker Type (Liker Type) as follows: so that the highest score for paragraph (1), and the minimum score for the paragraph (0). Then the estimates were classified and arranged according to the arithmetic mean of the estimate into the following categories:

- High if the arithmetic mean (degree of applicability) is (0.67) or more
- Average if the arithmetic mean (degree of applicability) is between (0.34) to (0.6).
- Low if the arithmetic mean (degree of applicability) is (0.33) or less.

Construct Validity: A Scale of Learning Competencies

To extract the indications of the validity of the construction of the scale, the coefficients of correlation of the paragraphs of the scale with the total score and between each paragraph and their correlation with the field to which they belong by presenting it to (12) referees in the field of autism, special education and psychology. (0.38-0.83), and with the field (0.42-0.90), it should be noted that all the correlation coefficients were of acceptable scores and statistically significant, and therefore none of the scale paragraphs and its number (63) paragraphs distributed into (5) domains were deleted.

Stability of the study tool: a measure of educational competencies

To ensure the stability of the study tool, the test-retest method was verified by applying the scale, and re-applying it after two weeks to a group of outside the study sample consisting of (25) teachers, and then the Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated between their estimates both times.

The stability coefficient was also calculated using the internal consistency method according to the Cronbach Alpha equation, and Table (3) shows the internal consistency coefficient according to the Cronbach Alpha equation and the return stability for the fields and the tool as a whole. These values were considered appropriate for the purposes of this study.

Table No. (3)

Coefficient of internal consistency (Cronbach alpha) and coefficient of repetition stability (Pearson) for fields and overall score

The field	Repetition constancy coefficient (Pearson)	Stability coefficient of internal consistency (Cronbach Alpha)
Teaching planning	0.90	0.74
The educational program	0.88	0.78
Diagnosis and evaluation	0.85	0.83
The educational environment	0.89	0.78
Inclusion and Transition Services	0.87	0.81
Total marks	0.88	0.86

It appears from Table No. (3) that the stability coefficients of repetition (Pearson) ranged between (0.85) and (0.90), and for the tool as a whole (0.88), which is acceptable for the purposes of this study. And that the coefficients of stability of internal consistency (Cronbach Alpha) ranged between (0.74) and (0.83), and for the tool as a whole (0.86), and these ratios were considered appropriate for the purposes of this study.

Second: The training program

To achieve the objectives of the study, the training program was designed after reviewing the educational literature related to educational competencies for female teachers of students with autism spectrum disorder in kindergarten, and previous related studies. And taking into account the training needs of female teachers, in addition to recent global trends in designing training programs, and taking into account the conditions for building training programs, and the program was built according to the following steps:

- Identifying the performance level of female teachers, the skills, competencies and practices implemented in the classroom using the scale of the learning competencies developed for the teachers of students with autism spectrum disorder for the purposes of the study.
- Determining the training needs of female teachers related to the competencies of students with autism spectrum disorder, including: Preparing the program in its initial form, where the scale consists of (5) main areas: (1)

planning for teaching (2) the educational program (3) diagnosis and evaluation (4) environment Educational (5) Inclusion and transitional services.

-The main objective of the training program is to provide teachers of students with autism spectrum disorder with the necessary competencies in the process of learning and teaching in the classroom, where these objectives take the following detailed elements:

-General objectives: developing educational competencies, linking theoretical knowledge in the university preparation period for the teacher, and providing her with new, modern and effective teaching strategies and methods, and educational programs for students with autism spectrum disorder to develop their skills in all areas of the curriculum for them.

-Special objectives: to provide teachers with the skills, knowledge, practices and attitudes necessary for the teaching process, and to measure the effect of the training program on the teachers' performance by calculating the difference between the degrees of their pre-performance, and by calculating the difference between the degrees of their post performance, using the scale for the purposes of this study. The training program for female teachers is according to the following sequence: objectives, training content, methods, activities, and program evaluation. Teachers were encouraged and strengthened to participate in activities that enhance their knowledge of teaching competencies for students with autism spectrum disorder integrated in kindergarten schools. The teachers were evaluated and provided with appropriate feedback.

-The training program was used within (5) areas through (8) sessions and through (36) training activities, and through (34) meetings for each meeting (3) hours, and the implementation of the program continued for a period of three months.

Certification of the training program: For the suitability of the training program for the purposes of the study, it was presented to a group of arbitrators to verify the validity of the training program. The validity of the content was used. (10 arbitrators, in its final form, to express their opinion on the training program, and all proposals, recommendations and amendments were taken by the arbitrators, so that the training program in its final form becomes applicable.

Study variables:

The independent variable: the training program for teachers of students with autism spectrum disorder.

The dependent variable, which is: the educational competencies of female teachers of students with autism spectrum disorder

Study design: The researcher followed in this study the quasi-experimental approach, which is based on two groups (control and experimental) "Quasi Experimental". This approach is based on the causal relationship between two variables, one of which is the independent or experimental variable and the other is the dependent variable, given its suitability to treat the study variables.

study design:

Study procedures:

To achieve the aim of the study, the following procedures were followed:

First: Applying the educational competencies scale to the teachers of students with autism spectrum disorders in the control and experimental groups (pre-measurement) to verify the parity of the two groups. Arithmetic averages and standard deviations were extracted for the fields and the total score of the grades of kindergarten teachers with autism spectrum disorder on the pre-educational competency scale according to For the group variable (experimental, control), and to explain the statistical differences between the arithmetic means, the "T" test was used, and Table (4) illustrates this.

Table No. (4)

Arithmetic averages, standard deviations, and T-test according to the group variable (experimental, control) on the fields and the total score of teachers of kindergarten students with autism spectrum disorder on the scale of learning competencies (pre).

The field	The group	No.	The arithmetic mean	Standard Deviation	"T" value	Freedom Degree	Statistical Significance
Pre-Teaching planning	Experimental	20	1.72	.349	.247	38	.806
	Control	20	1.69	.288			
Pre-The educational program	Experimental	20	1.54	.235	-1.117	38	.271
	Control	20	1.61	.187			
Pre-Diagnosis and evaluation	Experimental	20	1.28	.276	-.946	38	.350
	Control	20	1.36	.281			
Pre-The educational environment	Experimental	20	1.38	.330	-.588	38	.560

	al						
	Control	20	1.44	.305			
Pre-Inclusion and Transition Services	Experimental	20	1.22	.353	-1.642	38	.109
	Control	20	1.40	.331			
Total score	Experimental	20	1.45	.179	-1.363	38	.181
	Control	20	1.53	.170			

Table No. (4) shows that there are no statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) attributable to the group variable (experimental, control), and in all fields (teaching planning, educational program, diagnosis and evaluation, educational environment, inclusion and transitional services) And in the total score of the pre-educational proficiency scale, where the values of (t) calculated for it ranged between (-1.363) and (-1.363), and this result indicates the equivalence of the two study groups (experimental and control).

Second: Applying the training program to the experimental group, after conducting a meeting with teachers of kindergarten students with autism spectrum disorder targeted by the study, to clarify the objectives of the program and its importance in developing the level of educational competencies and its positive importance, as well as agreeing on the mechanism of implementation and application of the training program, and its period of time And meeting place.

Third: Conducting a dimensional measurement of the experimental and control groups on the scale of educational competencies. This is to verify the effectiveness of the training program in developing the level of educational competencies of kindergarten teachers with autism spectrum disorder targeted by the study.

Fourth: Collecting data and dumping them into special tables, then entering the data on the computer and processing it statistically using the "Statistical Package for Social Sciences" (SPSS.)

Fifth: Discussing the results

: Discussing the findings related to the main first question and its text

-Are there statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) in developing the level of educational competencies of the teachers of the kindergarten students with autism spectrum disorder integrated in Irbid governorate between the control group and the experimental group?

To answer this question: The arithmetic means and standard deviations of the grades of kindergarten teachers with autism spectrum disorder were calculated on the scale of educational competencies in the pre and post measures according to the group (experimental, control), as shown in Table (5):

Table (5)

Arithmetic means, standard deviations, and (T) test for grades of kindergarten teachers with autism spectrum disorder on the learning aptitude scale for the pre and post scales according to the group (experimental, control)

The group	Number	Pre-Measurement		Post-Measurement	
		The arithmetic mean	Standard Deviation	The arithmetic mean	Standard Deviation
Experimental	20	1.45	.179	2.57	.200
Control	20	1.53	.170	1.98	.278
Total	40	1.49	.177	2.28	.383

Table (5) shows that there are apparent differences between the arithmetic mean of teachers of kindergarten students with autism spectrum disorder on the scale of educational competencies as a whole in the pre and post measurements. According to the experimental group (pre), the arithmetic mean was (1.49) with a standard deviation of (.177). The arithmetic mean of the control group (dimensional), (2.28) with a standard deviation of (.383) and the total score. To know whether these apparent differences were statistically significant, the accompanying one way ANCOVA analysis was used for the post measurement of the scale of educational competencies. As a whole according to the group (experimental, control) after neutralizing the effect of the pre-measurement they have, and the following is a presentation of these results as shown in Table (6).

Table (6)

The results of the accompanying one-way ANCOVA analysis of the post-measurement of the grades of kindergarten teachers with autism spectrum disorder on the scale of educational competencies as a whole according to the group (experimental, control) after neutralizing the effect of the pre-measurement they have.

The source of the contrast	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Average sum of squares	"F" Value	Indication level	Ita square χ^2
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Pre-Measurement	.011	1	.011	.178	.676	.005
The Group	3.235	1	3.235	53.941	.000	.593
Error	2.219	37	.060			
Total	5.707	39				

Table (6) shows that there are statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the scores of kindergarten teachers with autism spectrum disorder on the educational competency scale according to the group (experimental, control), so the value of (P) was (53.941) With a statistical significance of (0.000), which is a statistically significant value, which means that there is an effect of the group. In order to determine in favor of whom the differences were attributed, the modified arithmetic means and standard errors were extracted according to the group (experimental and control), as shown in Table (7).

It is also evident from Table (6) that the effect of the teaching method was large. The value of the ita square (ζ^2) explained (59.3%) of the explained (predicted) variance in the dependent variable, which is a measure of educational competencies.

Table No. (7)

The adjusted arithmetic averages and their standard errors for the total score of the scale of educational competencies according to the group (experimental, control)

The Group	The modified post arithmetic mean	\Standard error
Experimental	2.567	.055
Control	1.985	.055

The results in Table No. (7) indicate that the differences in the adjusted arithmetic averages in the grades of kindergarten teachers with autism spectrum disorder on the educational competency scale were in favor of the experimental group, as the adjusted average was (2.567) compared to the control group members, as the adjusted average was (1.985). .(

The arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the pre and post scales for the educational competencies scale domains were also calculated according to the group (experimental, control), as shown in Table (8).

Table No. (8)

The arithmetic means and standard deviations of the pre and post measurements for the areas of the measure of educational competencies according to the group (experimental and control).

The Field	The Group	No.	Pre-Measurement		Post-Measurement	
			The arithmetic mean	Standard Deviation	The arithmetic mean	Standard Deviation
Teaching Planning	Experimental	20	1.72	.349	2.65	.255
	Control	20	1.69	.288	2.22	.311
	Total	40	1.71	.316	2.43	.356
The educational program	Experimental	20	1.54	.235	2.63	.245
	Control	20	1.61	.187	2.03	.297
	Total	40	1.57	.213	2.33	.406
Diagnosis and evaluation	Experimental	20	1.28	.276	2.48	.205
	Control	20	1.36	.281	1.83	.518
	Total	40	1.32	.278	2.16	.511
Teaching Environment	Experimental	20	1.38	.330	2.52	.191
	Control	20	1.44	.305	1.90	.434
	Total	40	1.41	.315	2.21	.456
Inclusion and Transition Services	Experimental	20	1.22	.353	2.48	.373
	Control	20	1.40	.331	1.88	.533
	Total	40	1.31	.350	2.18	.547

It is noticed from Table (8) that there are apparent differences between the arithmetic means in the pre and post measurements of the educational competencies scale domains resulting from the difference of the group (experimental, control), and in order to verify the essence of the apparent differences, the one way MANCOVA was applied. This is as shown in Table (9).

Table (9)

Results of the concomitant single-group analysis of variance (experimental, control) on the domains of the scale of educational competencies.

Impact	Multiple test type	Multiple test value	Total "F"	The degree of freedom of the hypothesis	The degree of freedom of error	Error probability	Impact size ζ^2
The Group	Hotelling's Trace	1.801	1.801	5.000	29.000	.000	.643.

Table (9) shows that there is a group effect of statistical significance at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) on the dimensional measurement of the areas of the scale of educational competencies combined, where the Hotelling value was (1.801) and with a statistical significance amounted to (0.000), and to determine which area the effect was The group, the accompanying one-way analysis of variance (ANCOVA) was performed for each domain separately according to the group after neutralizing the effect of the pre-measurement they had, as shown in Table (10).

Table (10)

An accompanying one-way analysis of variance (ANCOVA) of the group's effect on the dimensional measurement of each area of the educational competency scale after neutralizing the effect of their pre-measurement.

The source of the contrast		Sum of squares	Degree of freedom	Center of sum of squares	"F"	Error probability	Impact size ζ^2
Pre-Teaching planning Attendant	Post-Teaching planning	.463	1	.463	6.501	.016	.165
Pre-The educational program Attendant	Post-The educational program	.199	1	.199	2.571	.118	.072
Pre-Diagnosis and evaluation Attendant	Post-Diagnosis and evaluation	.058	1	.058	.383	.540	.011
Pre-The educational environment Attendant	Post--The educational environment	.571	1	.571	6.314	.017	.161
Pre-Inclusion and Transition Services Attendant	Post- Inclusion and Transition Services	.778	1	.778	3.831	.059	.104
The Group	Teaching planning	1.448	1	1.448	20.339	.000	.381
	The educational program	3.151	1	3.151	40.785	.000	.553
	Diagnosis and evaluation	4.334	1	4.334	28.437	.000	.463
	The educational environment	3.618	1	3.618	39.971	.000	.548
	Inclusion and Transition Services	3.970	1	3.970	19.538	.000	.372
Error	Teaching planning	2.349	33	.071			
	The educational program	2.549	33	.077			
	Diagnosis and	5.029	33	.152			

	evaluation						
	The educational environment	2.987	33	.091			
	Inclusion and Transition Services	6.705	33	.203			
Total corrector	Teaching planning	4.937	39				
	The educational program	6.414	39				
	Diagnosis and evaluation	10.193	39				
	The educational environment	8.102	39				
	Inclusion and Transition Services	11.649	39				

Table (10) shows that there are statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) according to the effect of the group (experimental, control) in all fields, and to determine in favor of which of the two study groups were the essential differences, the modified arithmetic averages and standard errors of the domains were calculated according to For the group, as shown in Table (11).

Table (11)

The modified arithmetic meanings and standard errors of the post-measurement of the areas of the measure of educational competencies according to the group

Group	Group	The modified arithmetic mean	Standard Error
Post-Teaching planning	Experimental	2.639	.062
	Control	2.230	.062
Post-The educational program	Experimental	2.632	.064
	Control	2.029	.064
Post-Diagnosis and evaluation	Experimental	2.509	.091
	Control	1.802	.091
Post-The educational environment	Experimental	2.532	.070
	Control	1.886	.070
Post-Inclusion and Transition Services	Experimental	2.516	.105
	Control	1.839	.105

It is evident from Table No. (11) that the essential differences between the arithmetic meanings modified for the dimensional measurement in all areas of the scale of educational competencies were in favor of the members of the experimental group who were exposed to the training program compared to the members of the control group, noting that the effect size for the fields ranged between (37.2% -55.3%).

: Discussing and interpreting results

With regard to discussing the results related to the main question of the study, the results of this question showed that there are statistically significant differences attributable to the proposed training program where the significance was in favor of the experimental group that was trained using the proposed training program, where the significance was in favor of the experimental group (who underwent training using the proposed program), It obtained arithmetic averages higher than the arithmetic averages of the control group (which did not undergo training using the proposed training program). As a result, it can be said that the training program has led to the development of the level of educational competencies for teachers of kindergarten students with autism spectrum disorder who are integrated in public schools in the fields of (teaching planning, educational program (curriculum), diagnosis and evaluation, the learning environment, integration and transitional services) compared to the performance of the group. Control subjects who studied in the usual way, which means that the program was effective in improving the level of educational competencies and its five fields among the

members of the experimental group, and had a tangible effect in improving the ability and adequacy of the experimental sample members in the education and training of students with autism spectrum disorder.

This result can also be explained in the light of what teachers participating in the training program have been exposed to in terms of planning the training program by identifying the real training needs to develop the level of educational competencies, which affect the trainees and their happiness by making them able to adapt to the emerging educational situations; Due to the conditions of their application outside the official working hours, and the events, roles and educational activities that take place in them, and the use of attractive techniques, practices and teaching methods such as brainstorming, cooperative learning, discussion and dialogue, training workshops and workshops, and the various activities that contributed to drawing teachers out of the traditional daily routine that they received before Service, and helped them to change traditional thinking patterns, and make their perception wider and more comprehensive of the variables and concepts that enable them to deal with students with autism spectrum disorder in schools of integration well, and the ability to understand their feelings, and provide them with a safe environment through classroom management that suits the characteristics of children with spectrum disorder autism.

This result can also be explained by planning for teaching by including in the individual program educational goals that achieve balance for students with autism spectrum disorder in the areas: (cognitive, emotional, and skill). The individual educational program includes skills: language skills, communication skills, independence skills, social skills, academic skills, behavioral skills, cognitive skills, economic and public safety skills ... etc. The curriculum contains behavioral goals, teaching methods for goals, activities, educational methods, modern technology and the adaptations necessary to achieve goals: playing skills, automatic attention, response (to facial expressions, gestures and voice tone), free time, and teachers used educational methods and models such as: the sensed and the like. The physical, the abstract, the visual stimuli in teaching, the brief verbal instructions, the individual education, the small groups, the peer education, the plurality of the senses, the education through play, the task analysis ... etc. And include appropriate applied behavior modification strategies to prevent behavioral problems to intervene in crises. Through a multidisciplinary team to assess the current performance level of kindergarten students with autism spectrum disorder and determine their strengths and needs in order to provide educational services, including the tools used in the evaluation and the areas of evaluation. And a way to organize the learning environment in the form of educational pillars, such as: (individual and group education corner, relaxation, sleep, play, music, drawing, and the teacher's corner). And to prepare students for integration and choose the inclusion school and the methods used for successful integration and transfer.

The results of this study are consistent with a number of previous studies, such as the study (Ramo, 2013), which aimed to reveal the effectiveness of a training program through the presence of a positive trend between the post and pre-applications of teachers' attitudes towards each of: the training program elements, training methods, and evaluation tools. , And the use of modern educational methods in education, and the trend with continuous self-education. The study also showed that there are statistically significant differences in the academic achievement of the program content in favor of the post-test. It also agrees with the study of (Lee, Sandbank, and Zymrman, 2014), which aimed to determine the training needs of special education teachers, using the survey methodology, the results indicated the need to take into account the opinions of the teachers in the training programs provided to them, and also focused on preparing teachers well during the service. Through continuous training and government support, which has a significant impact on the development of educational competencies in the work environment. And the study (Al-Ghamdi, 2019), which aimed to assess the level of teaching skills of teachers of students with autism spectrum disorder, and then build a proposed training program to develop teaching skills and measure its effectiveness. The results of the post-measurement indicated that there was statistical significance in favor of the experimental group, and that the improvement included all dimensions of the watchlist. This study also concurs with the study of (Probst, & Leppert, 2008) that aimed to measure the impact of a training program for teachers of children with autism spectrum disorder on the basis of planning and organizing teaching. The results indicated a significant improvement in the behavioral symptoms of students in the classroom on the dimensional measurement, and a significant decrease in teachers reactions about stress, and teachers' use of structured learning strategies, and the results of the study provided preliminary evidence of the social viability of the training program. In the qualitative study conducted by each of (Kwon, Hong & Amorimc, 2018), it examined the correlation between the experiences of teachers in working with children with disabilities (such as education, specialized training, and years of scientific experience), and their attitudes towards children with disabilities and their academic practices in relation to inclusive education. Early childhood stage, and the results indicated that there is a positive correlation between teacher training and obtaining a bachelor's degree in early childhood in inclusive education settings. These results are in line with the study (Al-Bairat, 2018), whose results indicated that government regular schools are not ready to integrate students with disabilities in Jordan, as the readiness associated with management and workers came first, while the readiness associated with the special education teacher came last.

The results of this study differ with the study (Al-Tabal, 2019), which aimed to identify the reality of inclusive education programs in kindergartens in Jordan. The lack of specific programs used in children's schools that implement inclusive education programs in the southern governorates. The results reflected the lack of specific educational programs used in kindergartens, which affected the effectiveness of inclusive education and the formation of negative attitudes towards it by some administrations, teachers and some parents. Weak regulation of family participation in inclusive education settings. Among the most important recommendations in this study is the development of a procedural guide that takes into account the organization of the educational, material and supportive environment for people with disabilities.

The results of the current study also differ with the study (Al-Khatib, 2011), the results of which indicated that with regard to autism spectrum disorder, there was one dimension that had a high level of effectiveness: the "services and programs" dimension. Whereas, there were three dimensions with an average level of effectiveness, which are respectively: the "evaluation" dimension, the "educational environment" dimension and the "management and personnel" dimension. As for the remaining four dimensions, they were of a low level of effectiveness, namely: the "vision, thought and mission" dimension, "family participation, support and empowerment", the "integration and transitional services" dimension, and the "self-evaluation" dimension.

Recommendations

In light of the results obtained in this study, the researcher recommends the following:

- 1-Modifying the policies and practices related to the inclusive programs in public schools in the kindergarten stage for people with autism spectrum disorder.
- 2-Conducting training courses and workshops for female teachers in the field of communication and leadership to improve their social competencies.
- 3-Conducting a study to solicit the opinions of parents, principals and specialists on improving the competencies of female teachers for students with autism spectrum disorder.
- 4-Conducting a correlational study of the competencies of kindergarten teachers with autism and their relationship to years of experience, specialization, and age in Jordan.

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